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Embedding social impact in engineering curriculum

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ABSTRACT

The prospect of having a positive social impact motivates many students to study engineering. However, this motivation is largely ignored in engineering curricula, which have traditionally focused on the transmission of content knowledge.

The growth of humanitarian engineering education in recent years is part of a trend towards addressing social impact in engineering education and appealing to this student motivation. For example, many Australian universities now offer the Engineers without Borders (EWB) Design Challenge, humanitarian engineering research projects, or even entire degree specialisations. However, despite the success of these programs, what is lacking is a way of embedding social impact in all engineering curricula.

At Swinburne University of Technology, this lack is being addressed with a new curriculum being co-designed with industry partners, grounded in education research, and built around work-oriented pedagogies including project-based learning. Projects will be aligned with 4 Pillars: Emerging Technologies, Entrepreneurship, research & Development, and Social Impact.

In this paper, we will report on the development of our new Social Impact curriculum pillar, drawing on research from the fields of social science, engineering education, and humanitarian engineering, and from real-world case studies of how engineering has been used to achieve lasting positive social impact.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Ethics in Engineering Education, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: Curriculum, Social Impact, Project-based learning

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INTRODUCTION

Swinburne University of Technology (SUT) is developing a bold new practice-based engineering undergraduate degree, through a consultative curriculum co-design process with industry. Rather than a traditional content-driven approach, this new *Bachelor of Engineering Practice (Honours)* degree aims to develop the professional skill-sets and mind-sets that graduates will need in the 21st century engineering workforce. Project-based learning will be a fundamental aspect of this curriculum, with projects aligned to 4 Pillars: Emerging Technologies, Entrepreneurship, research & Development, and Social Impact. The ongoing process of developing a curriculum framework for this last Pillar, Social Impact, is the subject of this paper.

1 CONTEXT

1.1 The growth of service-learning and social impact in higher education

Service-learning is about combining activities with a positive impact on community and society with the learning goals of an educational program. It is a recent but burgeoning development in tertiary education. Research publications in this area only started coming out in the 1990s. For example, in 1993, Markus & Howard [1] addressed a perceived gap in the literature, by conducting an ‘experiment’ to investigate the learning outcomes from student participation in community service programs. And as recently as 2000, a paper was published with the title “What is service learning?” [2].

Growth in this area has accelerated in the last decade, and the study of it has become a topic in its own right. For example, the *International Journal for Service Learning in Engineering: Humanitarian Engineering and Social Entrepreneurship* issued its first Volume in 2006 [3], and the *Journal of Service-Learning in Higher Education* followed suit in 2012 [3].

The advent of humanitarian engineering education in recent years is part of this trend towards addressing social impact in engineering. For example, some universities now offer humanitarian engineering research projects or degree specialisations [4, 5]. And since starting a decade ago, the Engineers without Borders (EWB) Challenge, a competition for undergraduate students to develop designs to address issues facing community partners in developing countries, has had thousands of participants from the United Kingdom, Australia, and elsewhere. Starting only in 2015, EWB-Australia has run the Design Summit, an extra-curricular program for Australian undergraduate students to learn about human-centred design in Cambodia, India, Nepal, Malaysia, and Samoa that has quickly grown to now have almost a thousand alumni [6].

Addressing social impact is an important trend in engineering education that is being centrally incorporated in the new co-designed curriculum at SUT.

1.2 Co-designing a new engineering curriculum with industry

At SUT, the process of co-designing a new engineering curriculum with industry, as well as with input from students and the relevant peak body, is well underway. It will be summarised briefly here, as it has been reported in detail elsewhere [7].

The curriculum co-design process is represented below in *Fig. 1*, with a structure adapted from the *Design your Discipline* stakeholder consultation process [8]. The process is iterative in nature but moves through three broad stages: “stakeholder consultation” to gather as many different perspectives as possible, “consensus building”, and “engagement for change”.

Fig. 1. Framework for consultative curriculum co-design

The “stakeholder consultation” process included three ideas workshops, in which altogether 66 individuals from 50 diverse engineering organisations discussed emerging industry trends, the skill-sets and mind-sets required of graduates, and more. These inputs were analysed and distilled into a draft curriculum framework, that was then the subject of a second round of workshops.

Two curriculum development workshops were held in this “consensus building” stage, with a total of 21 participants from 18 different organisations giving feedback and input into revising the draft curriculum.

1.3 Draft curriculum framework

The draft curriculum of the *Bachelor of Engineering Practice (Honours)* degree is summarised below in Fig. 2. It consists of four domains, each of which is divided into three sub-domains. Each of these sub-domains in turn subsumes a number of underlying skills. For example, **Communication** has been unpacked to include: listening, questioning, adaptive communication style, persuasion & pitching, presentation skills, networking, and writing. Similarly, **Management** includes project management, risk management, time management, people management & team building, feasibility & prioritising, and budgeting.

Each year, the student experience will be centred around four 6-week terms. Each term, students will work in small groups on a project drawn from one of 4 Pillars: Emerging Technologies, Entrepreneurship, research & Development, and Social Impact. Over the course of each year, by completing projects from each of these 4 Pillars, as well as through a variety of other learning experiences on a smaller scale, students will develop professional skills in each of the curriculum domains and sub-domains.

Self	People	Enterprise	Discipline
Personal attributes and mind-sets to be an engineers	Interpersonal and communication skills to engage with others as an engineer	Professional and business skills to work as an engineer	Knowledge, skills and abilities to do engineering
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Qualities • Self-Management • Lifelong Learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Working with others • Impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management • Business & Finance • Professional Conduct 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive Abilities • Knowledge & Skills • Creativity

Fig. 2. The domains and sub-domains of the draft curriculum

2 EMBEDDING SOCIAL IMPACT – THE PROCESS SO FAR

The draft curriculum above summarises the skill-sets, mind-sets, and knowledge-sets identified by industry partners as being necessary to work and succeed as a graduate engineer. These will be engendered over the 4 years of the *Bachelor of Engineering Practice (Honours)* degree, starting with the first cohort of students in 2018.

The next steps in the development of this program are the identification of appropriate learning experiences to develop these skills in students, delineation of what this means at the different year levels, and strategies for authentic assessment. In particular, frameworks will be developed to differentiate ‘what counts as a Social Impact project’, and what this means at different year levels (and likewise for the other project Pillars). Complementary assessment frameworks for these different types of projects will also be developed. Lastly, through consultation with potential project partners, specific projects will be detailed for the first ‘pathfinder’ cohort in 2018.

To these ends, various explorations of the literature and community are underway, for example reviewing similar service-learning programs at other universities, identifying prospective project partners and learning experiences, reviewing relevant education research, and more. The steps taken so far are summarised below.

2.1 Social impact and service-learning projects at other universities

Service-learning has been used in a wide variety of academic disciplines and university courses [9]. In this section we describe some service-learning programs in engineering that serve as a comparison for our approach.

Bielefeldt et al. [10] reviewed a number of such programs, primarily in the United States. One of the most well-known service-learning programs is the Engineering Projects in Community Service (now known only as EPICS) program, which started at Purdue University in 1995 [11]. It involves inter-disciplinary undergraduate student teams earning academic credit by working to solve technology-based problems for local community organisations, and a number of research papers have explored different aspects of its implementation [12-15].

Similar programs exist at other universities. With the vision of integrating service-learning into every semester of the engineering degree, the *Service-Learning Integrated throughout the College of Engineering (SLICE)* program at the University of

Massachusetts Lowell perhaps most closely parallels our own goals and will provide an important touchstone in the development of our program [16].

Engineers without Borders has partnered with universities around the world to offer service-learning opportunities to students [17, 18]. Jolly et al. [19] evaluated one of the flagship EWB educational programs, the EWB Challenge, and found that in order to draw meaningful lessons from its implementation to improve future iterations, it was not enough to simply ask students how they felt about it. They argued that a much more detailed understanding of the student experience, how they managed success and failure, and what criteria they used to evaluate the course, were needed to inform any future changes to the program. We will have to keep this conclusion in mind when evaluating our own initial offering of our program in 2018.

As a complement to these programs, there are a number of relevant online resources for Social Impact in engineering. For example, websites like *Appropedia* and *EngineeringforChange* not only give examples of appropriate technology, but also detail numerous case studies of engineering projects with real impact [20, 21]. Other sites, like the *Generator School Network*, offer more general service-learning resources [22]. Students will be able to reflect on these case studies and build on these resources in their own project work.

2.2 Identifying prospective project partners

A central Pillar of the new engineering degree will be students working on real-world Social Impact projects. Prospective partners that will offer these projects include local community groups and other non-government organisations (NGOs), or the corporate social responsibility arms of larger corporations. Another avenue for identifying projects is through partnering with other disciplines in the university, such as education or social work, that already have their own networks in the community [23].

In addition to working on term-long projects, students will have the opportunity to participate in international service-learning programs. Prospective program partners include the *EWB Humanitarian Design Summit* [6], *Project Everest* [24], or the *Laika Academy* [25]. Exposure to such global issues and experiences can foster social responsibility [26].

2.3 Education research literature on teaching aligned skills

Working successfully on Social Impact projects will entail the development of a number of underlying skills, such as working cross-culturally, ethical decision-making, engaging community members, designing inclusively, and more. A good starting point in the literature is the collection edited by Colledge of service-learning pedagogies [27]. In this section we'll review some of the other relevant education research literature, that we will use to design learning experiences to cultivate these skills.

Herkert [28] reviewed the literature around ethical problem solving in engineering and argued that 'macroethics', regarding societal decisions about technology and the collective social responsibility of the profession, is often overlooked in teaching ethics. Colby & Sullivan [29] reviewed ethics teaching in engineering more systematically, identifying the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches, but generally concluding that current practices are inadequate. From their review, they made a number of recommendations: "defining ethics and professional responsibility broadly", "integrating with other learning goals", "using active pedagogies", "engaging faculty", and "increasing institutional intentionality" (p. 335-336).

Another aspect of having Social Impact is engaging the communities you are working within. Mazzurco [30] researched methods of 'facilitating community participation' by

interviewing experienced practitioners and subsequently generated 5 sets of questions, one for each of the key principles of engagement he identified, as a guide for reflection, planning, and implementation of Social Impact projects, that could easily be adopted with students [31]. Gilbert et al. [32] focused more on the teaching of community engagement skills, reviewing the literature on various pedagogical strategies and analysing one case study of an inter-disciplinary program involving engineering students collaborating with social work students. They described, for example, highlighting the importance of understanding power dynamics, and recommending a strengths-based approach and good listening. Participatory rural appraisal and related methods are also evidence-based approaches for community engagement that students will be expected to understand and critique [33-36].

Understanding different cultures and developing the skills to work across them is vital in a globalised workforce. Hofstede, and those he inspired, identified different dimensions (e.g. power-distance, or individualism versus collectivism) for comparing cultures and subsequently developed associated learning resources [37-39]. Some researchers have also examined cross-cultural skills and their development within the particular context of engineering education [40-42]. One challenge in working across cultures is understanding the complex social dynamics of a community different to one's own. Some researchers have adopted systems thinking approaches to help students understand these complexities [43-45].

Rather than the approach pejoratively characterised as 'drag-and-drop', imposing so-called solutions on communities without meaningful engagement and collaboration, human-centred approaches to engineering design have a number of advantages including quality, acceptance, cost, and more [46]. Understanding students' ideas about human-centred design and implementing strategies to encourage them to consider more inclusive designs will be a priority in our Social Impact program [46, 47].

Many of these skills are predicated upon the cultivation of a strong emotional intelligence, and it is certainly a requirement to succeed in the workforce [48, 49]. Explicitly cultivating emotional intelligence through our Social Impact programs should have many flow-on effects to other aspects of student development.

2.4 Evaluating student learning

Apart from more typical project-based assessment, other factors to consider in evaluating our program are whether students demonstrate any changes in their cross-cultural sensitivity, perceptions of the importance of Social Impact, or more broadly how they see the role of engineers in society. Various survey instruments have been developed to investigate these questions. For example, surveys have been developed and validated to measure multicultural competency [50], ethnocentrism [51], as well as attitudes towards community service [52], sustainability skills and dispositions [53], and the perceived social responsibility of engineers [54]. It is envisaged that these tools could be adapted to not only investigate changes in student attitudes and understanding, but also for feedback and evaluation of our Social Impact program.

2.5 Synthesis

The initial and ongoing development of a curriculum and assessment framework for the Social Impact Pillar will involve a number of inputs and interactions. This includes input from similar programs, feedback loops with industry partners and other ongoing monitoring and evaluation, and engaging with the relevant research literature (*Fig. 3*).

Fig. 3. Inputs and interactions informing the Social Impact curriculum pillar

3 CONCLUSION

The new *Bachelor of Engineering Practice (Honours)* degree at SUT is an exciting development in engineering education, doing away with outmoded traditional approaches to instruction, instead co-designing a new curriculum centred on work-oriented pedagogies and grounded in education research. Social Impact is one of four Pillars of project-based learning that will comprise a key aspect of the student learning experience.

In this paper, the first steps towards embedding Social Impact in this curriculum have been described. An update of this process will be presented at the SEFI conference in September.

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